

Scenario of Colorectal Cancer at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bangladesh: A Retrospective Observational Study

Professor Brig. Gen. Dr. Md. Quadrat-E-Elahi ✉

Senior Consultant, Ahsania Mission Cancer & General Hospital, Uttara, Bangladesh

Brig. Gen. Prof. Dr. S. M. Rahid Sarwar

Oncologist, Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Lt. Col. Dr. Ashraful Alam

Oncologist, Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Lt. Col. Dr. Fatima Sarker

Classified Specialist in Medical Oncology, Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Maj. Dr. Tariq Hasan

Oncologist, Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Fariha Chowdhury

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, North South University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

More Information

How to cite this article: Quadrat-E-Elahi M, Sarwar SMR, Alam A, Sarker F, Hasan T, Chowdhury F. Scenario of Colorectal Cancer at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bangladesh: A Retrospective Observational Study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(2): 181-6.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(2).29

Keywords:

Colorectal cancer,
Clinicopathological profile,
Sociodemographic characteristics,
Risk factors,
Treatment patterns,
Bangladesh.

Abstract

Background: Colorectal cancer is an increasing health problem in developing countries including Bangladesh, as local data on patient characteristics and treatment patterns remain limited. This study aimed to describe the sociodemographic profile, disease characteristics, and treatment patterns of colorectal cancer patients treated at a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh.

Methods: This retrospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Oncology, Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka, over a four-year period from 2020 to 2023. Medical records of 100 patients with histologically confirmed colorectal cancer were reviewed. Data on demographic characteristics, clinical and pathological findings, treatment regimens, and treatment-related toxicities were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results: Most patients were middle-aged (46%) adults, with a clear male predominance (74%) and a majority coming from rural areas (85%). Adenocarcinoma (62%) was the most common histological type, and most tumors were of moderate grade (87%). While colonic involvement was more prevalent (72%), adjuvant chemotherapy was the most commonly used treatment approach (41%). Treatment-related toxicities were common, with hand and foot syndrome (35%) being the most frequently reported adverse effect.

Conclusion: Colorectal cancer patients in this setting commonly present at a relatively younger age and with more advanced disease. The predominance of moderate to high-grade tumors and the frequent need for systemic therapy highlights delayed presentation. These findings emphasize the need for improved awareness, early detection strategies, and strengthened cancer care services in Bangladesh.

Abbreviation:

Colorectal cancer: CRC; Adenomatous Polyposis Coli: APC; Kirsten-ras: K-ras; Fecal Immunochemical Test: FIT

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) represents a significant and growing global health burden, ranking as the third most commonly diagnosed cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. In 2022, there were approximately 1.93 million new cases and about 9,04,000 deaths globally, with the burden expected to increase to 3.2 million new cases and 1.6 million deaths by 2040 [1,2]. The incidence of CRC has previously been higher in high-income countries; however, a clear epidemiological shift is emerging, characterized by a rapidly rising burden in low- and middle-income regions, including South Asian countries [3,4].

The management of CRC has advanced significantly, with treatment strategies being increasingly based on a multimodal approach involving surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, guided by the disease stage and molecular characteristics [5]. While international guidelines inform these practices, their applicability and outcomes in specific settings like Bangladesh must be evaluated against local realities, including patient presentation, available resources, and sociocultural factors influencing care [6]. Despite advances in understanding its molecular etiology and treatment, the burden is shifting geographically, posing new challenges for healthcare systems like Bangladesh's. Pathophysiologically, CRC arises from the colonic epithelium through a multistep process of adenoma-to-carcinoma sequence, driven by an accumulation of genetic and epigenetic alterations in key pathways such as APC/ β -catenin (Wnt), TP53, and K-ras, which lead to uncontrolled cellular proliferation and evasion of apoptosis [7].

In Bangladesh, a country undergoing significant demographic and lifestyle changes, cancer is an emerging public health challenge. However, a precise understanding of the CRC burden is hampered by a lack of robust, population-based national cancer registry data [8]. Existing information often relies on fragmented reports from tertiary care hospitals, which provide critical insights into the clinical and demographic profile of affected patients seeking advanced care [9]. Understanding these profiles, including age distribution, socioeconomic background, and histopathological characteristics, is essential for guiding resource allocation and tailoring local treatment protocols [10].

Therefore, this study aims to describe the prevalence and characterize the sociodemographic and clinic-pathological profile of colorectal cancer patients presenting at a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh. This research seeks to fill a critical knowledge gap and provide a foundational overview to inform future public health initiatives and clinical strategies against CRC.

Methods

Study Design & Setting

This was a retrospective, observational study designed to determine the prevalence and characterize the profile of colorectal cancer patients at a tertiary care military hospital. The study was conducted at the Department of Oncology, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Dhaka. CMH is a large tertiary care referral center that provides comprehensive cancer diagnosis and treatment services to both military personnel and the general civilian population, catering to a substantial patient burden from across the country.

Study Period & Population

For the purpose of this study, data was curated, cleaned and analyzed throughout the study period of four years from 2020 to 2023. The study population included all inpatient and outpatient patients with a confirmed diagnosis of colorectal cancer who had attended the oncology department during the study period.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- Adult patients of both genders.
- New or previously diagnosed cases of histopathologically confirmed colorectal cancer.
- Patients who were either admitted to the hospital or attended the outpatient department for management.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records where key data on diagnosis or treatment were missing.
- Pregnant & lactating women were excluded from the study

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A consecutive sampling technique was employed. All eligible patients fulfilling the selection criteria diagnosed within the study period were screened, and the first 100 patients with complete medical records were included in the final analysis.

Data Collection

Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records using a structured, pre-designed data collection form. The form captured information on:

- Sociodemographic variables: Age, gender, residence, educational status, occupation, and monthly income.
- Clinical and pathological variables: Histopathological type, grade, and disease recurrence.
- Treatment: The primary treatment regimen received (e.g., adjuvant chemotherapy, neo-adjuvant chemotherapy, palliative surgery, radiotherapy).

Clinical and pathological variables were assessed through a detailed review of patient medical records. Histopathological type was confirmed based on findings from biopsy or surgical resection specimens. Tumor grading was determined according to the World

Health Organization classification system. Information on treatment-related toxicities documented in the records was also collected. These included hematological toxicities such as anemia, neutropenia, and thrombocytopenia; dermatological toxicities including alopecia and melanonychia; and gastrointestinal toxicities such as diarrhea, bloating, nausea, and vomiting.

Data Analysis

Collected data were entered into and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages (n, %). Continuous variables were summarized as mean ± standard deviation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Combined Military Hospital, Dhaka. As the study involved the analysis of anonymized retrospective data from patient records, the requirement for individual informed consent was waived by the ethics committee. All data were kept confidential and used solely for the purpose of this research.

Results

Table 1 summarizes the distribution of sociodemographic characteristics of the study participants. The majority of participants were middle-aged (40-59 years) adults, predominantly male, and most resided in rural areas.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Patients (n=100)

Characteristic	Frequency
Age (years)	
<30	5
30-39	20
40-49	22
50-59	24
60-69	20
>70	9
Mean ± SD	50.6 ± 13.7
Gender	
Male	74
Female	26
Region	
Rural	85
Urban	15

Table 2 presents the distribution of occupational and socioeconomic characteristics of the study participants. A greater proportion of participants had at least a secondary level of education, with a substantial proportion engaged in formal employment, particularly in government and private sectors. In addition, income

levels were generally in the low-to-middle range, and the majority of participants were married.

Table 2: Socioeconomic and Occupational Characteristics of the Study Participants (n=100)

Characteristic	Frequency
Educational status	
Illiterate	18
Primary	15
Secondary	25
Graduate	28
Post graduate	14
Occupation	
Daily labor	18
Government employee	36
Private service	31
Teacher	5
Housewife	10
Monthly income	
>10,000	22
10,000-30,000	30
30,000-50,000	45
>50,000	7
Marital status	
Unmarried	16
Married	84

Figure 1: Patterns of Smoking among Patients (n=100)

Cigarette smoking and betel nut use were the most common practices in the study cohort, and a smaller proportion reported to having quit smoking, while a notable group had no history of smoking. Patterns of smoking and distribution of smoking-related habits of the study participants illustrated by Figure 1 Adenocarcinoma was the predominant histological type with smaller proportions of neuroendocrine and mucinous tumors. Most cases were of moderate to high histological grade, indicating a tendency toward more aggressive disease, while recurrence was observed in a limited number of patients elaborated in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Patients by Histological Characteristics & Other Findings (n=100)

Variable	N
Histopathological type	
Adenocarcinoma	62
Neuroendocrine	26
Mucinous	12
Histological grade	
Grade I	5
Grade II	41
Grade III	46
Grade IV	8
Recurrence	7

Figure 2: Distribution of Patients Based on Location of Tumor (n=100)

Figure 2 demonstrates that colorectal tumors were more frequently located in the colon than in the rectum, with distal and proximal colonic sites showing a comparable predominance, while rectal involvement was relatively less common.

Table 4: Treatment Regimen of the Patients (n=100)

Treatment	N
Adjuvant chemotherapy	41
Neo-adjuvant chemotherapy	15
Palliative surgery followed by chemotherapy	21
Radiotherapy (with or without chemotherapy)	23

Table 4 indicates that adjuvant chemotherapy as monotherapy was the most commonly administered treatment approach. A considerable proportion of patients received radiotherapy, either alone or in combination with chemotherapy, while others underwent palliative surgical management followed by chemotherapy. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy was used less frequently in comparison to other treatment modalities.

Table 5 describes the distribution of treatment-related toxicities among the study participants indicating that

hand and foot syndrome was the most frequently observed toxicity, followed by hematological and gastrointestinal adverse effects. Melanonychia was less commonly reported compared with other toxicity patterns.

Table 5: Distribution of Toxicities of the Patients (n=100)

Toxicity	N
Hand & foot syndrome	35
Melanonychia	8
Hematological toxicity	23
Gastrointestinal toxicity	18

Discussion

This cross-sectional study provides a comprehensive overview of the sociodemographic, clinical, and treatment characteristics of colorectal cancer (CRC) patients in a tertiary care setting in Bangladesh. The findings reveal several critical patterns that align with, yet also diverge from, both regional and global trends, offering valuable insights for public health planning and clinical management.

Sociodemographic and Clinical Profile

The mean age of presentation in our cohort was 50.6 years, which is notably younger than the typical peak incidence of 65-74 years reported in high-income countries [1]. This trend of earlier onset is increasingly observed in South Asia and is consistent with studies from India and Pakistan, suggesting distinct regional risk factors, potentially including genetic predispositions, dietary habits, and earlier exposure to environmental carcinogens [3,9]. Furthermore, the marked male predominance (74%) and many patients from rural areas (85%) highlight significant demographic disparities. While the global male-to-female ratio for CRC is approximately 1.4:1, our finding of nearly 3:1 warrants further investigation into gender-specific risk behaviors, such as tobacco and betel nut chewing, which are more prevalent among males in rural Bangladesh [11]. The high proportion of rural patients also underscores the challenges in healthcare access and may indicate delayed presentation; a factor associated with advanced disease stages and poorer outcomes.

Pathological Spectrum and Clinical Patterns

Adenocarcinoma constituted most cases (62%), which is consistent with the global histologic distribution of CRC [3]. However, the high prevalence of moderately differentiated Grade II & III tumors (87%) suggests that most patients present with advanced disease that requires aggressive, multimodal management. The treatment data, showing that 41% of patients received adjuvant chemotherapy, reflects adherence to standard international protocols for stage III and high-risk stage II colon cancer [5]. Nevertheless, the fact that

almost 60% of patients received neo-adjuvant therapy, radiotherapy or palliative therapy, indicates a substantial burden of locally advanced disease at presentation. This pattern reinforces the critical need for enhanced early detection programs in Bangladesh, as outcomes are significantly improved when CRC is diagnosed at an earlier, more curable stage [12]. Treatment-related toxicities comprised of majorly hand and foot syndrome followed by hematological toxicities like anemia, neutropenia, thrombocytopenia and gastrointestinal disorders such as diarrhea, bloating etc. which are consistent with previous research [13].

Implications and Future Directions

The predominance of rural patients also has important clinical implications. Limited access to specialized healthcare services, delayed health-seeking behavior, and lower awareness in rural settings likely contribute to late-stage presentation. This is supported by the pathological findings, where a large majority of tumors were of moderate to high grade (Grade II and III), indicating more advanced disease at diagnosis. Correspondingly, treatment patterns further reflect delayed presentation, as a substantial proportion of patients required adjuvant chemotherapy, radiotherapy, neoadjuvant treatment, or palliative interventions rather than curative surgery alone. Together, the rural predominance, higher tumor grade, and reliance on intensive or palliative treatment modalities form a consistent picture of delayed diagnosis, which is known to be associated with poorer outcomes.

The overall profile of the study population, characterized by relatively young age, male predominance, rural residence, and presentation with advanced yet treatable disease, highlights important priorities for public health planning. There is an urgent need to develop and implement cost-effective screening approaches, such as fecal immunochemical tests, that are adapted to the Bangladeshi context and targeted toward high-risk groups [14]. In addition, the wide range of occupations and income levels observed among patients, from daily laborers to government employees, indicates that CRC affects individuals across socioeconomic strata rather than being confined to a specific group. This pattern underscores the need for broad-based awareness campaigns that reach diverse segments of the population and promote early recognition and timely healthcare seeking.

Limitations and Future Research Scope

While this study provides valuable foundational data, it does have limitations. The single-center, hospital-based design may affect generalizability, suggesting the need for future multi-center studies to establish national epidemiological patterns. Furthermore, the absence of data on molecular biomarkers, detailed staging, and survival outcomes highlights the necessity for prospective research integrating molecular profiling

with long-term clinical follow-up to better understand disease biology and prognosis in the Bangladeshi population.

Conclusion

This study delineates a distinct profile of colorectal cancer in the Bangladeshi population, characterized by a notably younger age of onset and a significant male and rural predominance. The high prevalence of moderately differentiated adenocarcinomas and the reliance on adjuvant chemotherapy as treatment underscore the advanced stage at which the disease is typically diagnosed. These findings argue for piloting cost-effective screening programs, such as FIT-based screening, in rural primary care centers, coupled with physician education on early CRC symptom. Additionally, it highlights the need for further research to elucidate the underlying risk factors driving this unique epidemiological pattern.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Reference

- [1] Bray F, Laversanne M, Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Soerjomataram I, et al. Global cancer statistics 2022: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2024 May–Jun;74(3):229–263. doi:10.3322/caac.21834.
- [2] Morgan E, Arnold M, Gini A, Lorenzoni V, Cabasag CJ, Laversanne M, et al. Global burden of colorectal cancer in 2020 and 2040: incidence and mortality estimates from GLOBOCAN. *Gut.* 2023 Feb;72(2):338–344. doi:10.1136/gutjnl-2022-327736.
- [3] Arnold M, Sierra MS, Laversanne M, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A, Bray F. Global patterns and trends in colorectal cancer incidence and mortality. *Gut.* 2017 Apr;66(4):683–691. doi:10.1136/gutjnl-2015-310912.
- [4] Dhillon PK, Mathur P, Nandakumar A, Fitzmaurice C, Kumar GA, Mehrotra R, et al. The burden of cancers and their variations across the states of India: the Global Burden of Disease Study 1990–2016. *Lancet Oncol.* 2018 Oct;19(10):1289–1306. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(18)30447-9.
- [5] Benson AB III, Venook AP, Al-Hawary MM, Arain MA, Chen YJ, Ciombor KK, et al. Colon cancer, version 2.2021, NCCN clinical practice guidelines in oncology. *J Natl Compr Canc Netw.* 2021 Mar;19(3):329–359. doi:10.6004/jnccn.2021.0012.
- [6] Pramesh CS, Badwe RA, Bhoo-Pathy N, Booth CM, Chinnaswamy G, Dare AJ, et al. Priorities for cancer research in low- and middle-income countries: a global perspective. *Nat Med.* 2022 Apr;28(4):649–657. doi:10.1038/s41591-022-01738-0.

- [7] Fearon ER. Molecular genetics of colorectal cancer. *Annu Rev Pathol.* 2011;6:479–507. doi:10.1146/annurev-pathol-011110-130235.
- [8] Hussain SA, Sullivan R. Cancer control in Bangladesh. *Jpn J Clin Oncol.* 2013 Nov;43(11):1159–1169. doi:10.1093/jjco/hyt140.
- [9] Malhotra RK, Manoharan N, Nair K, Bakshi G, Muwonge R, Rath GK, et al. Colorectal cancer in young patients in India: a scoping review. *South Asian J Cancer.* 2022 Jan–Mar;11(1):1–7. doi:10.1055/s-0041-1735564.
- [10] Bhurgri Y, Khan T, Kayani N, Ahmad R, Usman A, Bhurgri H, et al. Incidence and current trends of colorectal malignancies in an unscreened, low-risk Pakistan population. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2011;12(3):703–708.
- [11] Rahman MA, Mahmood S, Karim MJ, Islam R, Alam MS. Pattern of smokeless tobacco use and its association with head and neck cancers in Bangladesh: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Tob Use Insights.* 2022;15:1179173X221087474. doi:10.1177/1179173X221087474.
- [12] Gupta S, Bhattacharya CG, Tangka FKL, Nandakumar A, Aitken JF, Klabunde CN, et al. Cost-utility analysis of colorectal cancer screening in a low-resource setting: the case of Bangladesh. *Value Health Reg Issues.* 2022 May;29:84–92. doi:10.1016/j.vhri.2021.11.003.
- [13] Han CJ, Ning X, Burd CE, Spakowicz DJ, Tounkara F, Kalady MF, et al. Chemotoxicity and associated risk factors in colorectal cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cancers (Basel).* 2024 Jul;16(14):2597. doi:10.3390/cancers16142597.
- [14] Issa IA, NouredDine M. Colorectal cancer screening: an updated review of the available options. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2017 Jul 28;23(28):5086–5096. doi:10.3748/wjg.v23.i28.5086.

